

PHILOSOPHY

Filozofie přírodních věd

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FRACTAL REPRESENTATION OF COGNITIVE PROCESSES

The study of the mechanisms of human cognition has held a significant place in philosophy for many years. Within the interdisciplinary approach to studying the brain, the methodology of modern philosophy of science utilizing synergetics and fractal theory represents a particularly significant platform. This approach allows for the integration of various aspects of analyzing and understanding the complexity of brain activity as a whole. Representation is a key concept that plays a crucial role in understanding the surrounding world. It is based on humans' endeavor to describe and explain reality, as well as to present information about objects, events, or processes. Originally borrowed from psychology, the term «representation» had a narrower definition, defined as «the act of recalling various action procedures from memory to manipulate an object, even without direct perception of the object» [1, p. 95]. In the context of scientific research, representation serves as a secondary reflection of objects, their properties, and processes in the human mind. The concept of representational knowledge always implies the indication of reflecting or displaying something, including human consciousness, and relates to «deduced knowledge» generated by this process. Despite the wide usage of representation, the key question remains about its implementation, requiring a deep analysis of the essence and functions in various fields of activity. Representation is not limited to linguistic forms; besides language, it includes other forms of expression. These diverse forms not only aid in organizing information but also simplify the construction of new theories and concepts.

For a long time, neuroscience has been influenced by the dominant paradigm of stable states and determinism. According to this paradigm, the brain is viewed as a complex system maintaining stable equilibrium. Significant progress has been made in traditional psychology and neurophysiology, including the understanding of individual mechanisms of neuron functioning, laws of nerve impulse transmission, as well as concepts of reflexes and other aspects. However, the fundamental principles of brain function remained unclear within this paradigm, based on the study of stable processes and phenomena. In recent decades, an approach has been developed suggesting that biological systems exhibit unique complexity. They consist of a vast number of cells, each of which is a complex system, suggesting a fractal nature of their organization. These systems demonstrate a high degree of complex behavior, including cooperative cell interaction, manifested, for example, in coordinated muscle movements or other actions. In the human brain, a vast number of cells collaborate to facilitate sensory perception, thinking, emotions, oral and written speech, and other complex functions. New qualities at the macroscopic level, not inherent in individual cells at the microscopic level, represent a synergy phenomenon.

Taking into account the thoroughly studied neurobiological mechanisms of exciting cortical neuron ensembles, as well as the fractal properties of the self-organization process of complex systems during phase transitions caused by bifurcations, one can formulate a hypothesis about the fractal organization of human brain cognitive activity. On the other hand, factuality, confirmed by numerous studies of the behavior of complex systems of various natures, serves as a natural intermediate state between complete order and complete chaos. The concept of «representation» is relevant when interpreting the cognitive system as a hierarchy of fractal processes to denote the forms of determination of one process by another. Sequential representations form a multi-level path of data transmission. The overall result, presented as an ordered picture of the world, arises from the complex interaction of mutually deterministic cognitive processes exchanging data in representative forms acceptable to them.

The concept of factuality and representation are closely intertwined through methods of analyzing and visualizing complex structures and processes across various domains, including nature. In the context of cognitive science, fractal patterns are detected in various aspects of thinking, including decision-making, information retention, and the creative process. Fractal theory serves as a tool for conveying complexity and nonlinearity in nature and science, representing complex hierarchical structures and heterogeneous processes. Fractals effectively visualize and analyze details and features that may be overlooked in traditional descriptive methods.

The use of fractal models and images allows for the efficient representation of information about the structure and nature of objects and processes in a compact and expressive form. The concept of representation remains important for scientific research, describing cognitive perception of the world. It is assumed that representations are formed as a result of fractal processes at different levels, where the results at lower levels are used to form representations at higher levels, enhancing the efficiency of systemic interactions. Ultimately, representations as mental structures of humans encompass various aspects: «primary representations» formed even before the level of verbalization. They are simple mental images arising from direct perception of the surrounding world. During cognitive experience, an individual actively interacts with the surrounding environment, with several or all sensory analyzers participating in cognitive interaction with various components of the environment. Such interactions represent a synthesis of elementary representations, leading to the complexity of their structure. Depending on the conditions of interaction with the surrounding environment, individual types of representations can be reinforced and become more stable.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the concept of fractal organization of cognitive activity in the brain opens up new perspectives in studying representation and its influence on cognitive processes. Philosophical analysis of the mechanism of representation becomes necessary for advancing science in understanding human thinking and developing new methods of researching complex systems.

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